

Electrochemical synthesis of zinc(II) glycolates and their coordination compounds

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Abstract : Zinc(II) glycolates have been synthesized by electrolyzing the solutions of aldehydes (benzaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, acetaldehyde and propionaldehyde) and ketones (acetone, isobutyl methyl ketone and ethyl methyl ketone) in acetonitrile at sacrificial zinc anode. These glycolates do not form coordination compounds when refluxed with ligands such as 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl. However, coordination compounds of these glycolates have been synthesized by electrolyzing the solution of aldehyde/ketone in the presence of ligands in acetonitrile at sacrificial zinc anode. All these products have been characterized by infrared spectral data, elemental analysis and various physical properties. Current efficiencies of all these systems are quite high.

Keywords : Electrosynthesis, H-type cell, zinc(II) glycolates, coordination compounds, current efficiencies.

Introduction

Electrochemical synthesis of metal alkoxides, phenoxides and thiolates by the oxidation of sacrificial anodes in the solutions of alcohols, phenols, thiols, dithiols etc. has been reported in literature¹⁻⁸. It has been observed that this technique provides direct and short-cut synthetic route and the reactions proceed with high current efficiencies. In continuation to our efforts to explore the use of the electrochemical technique as a synthetic tool, we report in the present communication the electrochemical synthesis of zinc(II) glycolates and their coordination compounds with 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl.

Results and discussion

Zinc(II) glycolates :

Solid products isolated from the anode compartment are insoluble in different organic solvents such as dimethyl sulphoxide, *N,N*-dimethyl formamide, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, methanol, etc. These products do not melt upto 220 °C but show a distinct colour change in the temperature range of 190–220 °C, thereby indicating that the products decompose in this temperature range.

Analytical data of the products are summarised in Table 1. The data correspond to 2 : 1 stoichiometry of aldehydes/ketones and zinc respectively.

Infrared spectra of these products have been scanned

in potassium bromide pellets in the region of 4000–450 cm^{-1} . Perusal of the infrared spectral data reveals that all the products (except that of salicylaldehyde) do not show any absorption band corresponding to the carbonyl group⁹, however, characteristic bands appear in the regions of 1091–1000 and 475–456 cm^{-1} .

Survey of literature reveals that $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})^{10-14}$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})\text{M}^{10-15}$ absorption bands in metal alkoxide appear in the regions of 470–450 and 1150–1000 cm^{-1} respectively. Adam *et al.*¹⁰ reported the appearance of $\nu(\text{Zn}-\text{O})$ bands at 465 cm^{-1} in zinc(II) methoxides. Recently, Banait *et al.*^{6,7} also reported the $\nu(\text{Zn}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})\text{Zn}$ absorption bands at 470–450 and 1160–1000 cm^{-1} respectively in zinc(II) alkoxides/phenoxides. Thus the characteristic bands observed in the regions of 470–456 and 1091–1000 cm^{-1} in the present studies may be attributed to $\nu(\text{Zn}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})\text{Zn}$ modes respectively. Survey of literature reveals¹⁰⁻¹⁵ that two types of $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})\text{M}$ bands appear in the infrared spectral data of metal alkoxides. Generally the bands in the lower region (1060–1000 cm^{-1}) are assigned to bridged alkoxide groups and those in the region of 1160–1060 cm^{-1} are assigned to terminal alkoxides. Appearance of $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})\text{Zn}$ bands in the lower region (1090–1020 cm^{-1}) shows the presence of bridged alkoxide/phenoxide groups¹⁰⁻¹⁵ thus indicating the polymeric structure of the products. Polymeric

Table 1. Electrolysis characteristics, analytical and other related data of electrochemical reactions of aldehydes and ketones at zinc anode

System	Potential applied (V)	Electricity passed (Coulombs)	Product	Colour	Elemental analysis (%) :			Current efficiency (gram equivalent faraday ⁻¹)
					Found (Calcd.)			
					Zn	C	H	
Acetaldehyde	30	680	C ₄ H ₈ O ₂ Zn	White	37.0 (42.7)	29.1 (31.3)	4.9 (5.2)	0.37
Propionaldehyde	35	720	C ₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ Zn	White	33.8 (36.1)	36.1 (39.1)	5.8 (6.6)	0.98
Benzaldehyde	35	720	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ Zn	White	20.2 (23.6)	55.6 (60.6)	3.7 (4.3)	0.96
Salicylaldehyde	30	680	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₄ Zn	Dark green	19.3 (21.1)	50.4 (54.3)	3.1 (3.9)	0.76
Cinnamaldehyde	30	680	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ Zn	Brown	22.4 (19.9)	63.0 (65.6)	3.9 (4.9)	0.78
Acetone	30	700	C ₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ Zn	Light brown	34.7 (36.1)	35.6 (39.7)	5.1 (6.6)	0.95
Ethyl methyl ketone	30	720	C ₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ Zn	Light brown	30.9 (31.2)	43.1 (45.7)	6.9 (7.6)	0.70
Isobutyl methyl ketone	30	680	C ₁₂ H ₂₄ O ₂ Zn	Light brown	24.0 (24.6)	51.8 (54.3)	7.1 (9.0)	0.85

nature of these products is also supported by their insoluble behaviour in various solvents.

The formation of zinc(II) glycolates in these systems can be explained through the following reaction Scheme :

Literature reveals^{16,17} that aldehydes and ketones yield radical anions on reduction at inert cathode :

These radical anions dimerise to yield dianions :

Under the influence of applied field these dianions move towards sacrificial zinc anode to yield zinc(II) glycolates :

Infrared spectral data of the product of electrochemical reaction of salicylaldehyde at sacrificial zinc anode show no absorption band due to $\nu(\text{O-H})$ stretching vibrations⁹ but show an absorption band at 1622.3 cm^{-1} corresponding to $\nu(\text{C=O})$ stretching vibrations⁹. The product also shows characteristic absorption bands at 1020 and 464 cm^{-1} , which can be assigned to $\nu(\text{C-O})\text{Zn}$ and $\nu(\text{Zn-O})$ stretching modes respectively¹⁰⁻¹⁵. In addition to these bands, the product show $\nu(\text{C-H})$ stretching vibrations as doublet at 2922.5 and at 2903.9 cm^{-1} due to interactions between C-H stretching fundamental and overtones of C-H deformation¹⁸. The presence of the bands at 1020 and 464 cm^{-1} and bands due to carbonyl group indicates that carbonyl group of salicylaldehyde does not take part in the electrochemical reaction. The presence of $\nu(\text{C-O})\text{Zn}$ and $\nu(\text{Zn-O})$ stretching vibrations and absence of $\nu(\text{O-H})$ band in the infrared spectral data confirms that the phenolic proton of salicylaldehyde has been replaced with sacrificial zinc anode. This is also supported by the analytical data. Appearance of the $\nu(\text{C-O})\text{Zn}$ vibrations in the lower region (1020 cm^{-1}) indicates that the product exists as a polymer through alkoxy bridging. This fact is also supported by the solubility data.

In case of salicylaldehyde, as the phenolic group is more easily reducible than aldehyde group, therefore, only phenolic group is reduced at inert cathode and the reaction scheme may be written as :

At inert cathode :

At sacrificial anode :

In aldehydes and ketones, the band due to carbonyl group generally appears⁹ around 1650 cm⁻¹. Shift of this band towards lower region indicates that the product of the electrolysis of salicylaldehyde-zinc system may have the following structure :

Current efficiencies of these systems have also been determined and are listed in Table 1. The data reveal that current efficiencies of all these systems (except that of acetaldehyde-zinc system) are quite high. High current efficiencies of these systems indicate that the reactions leading to the formation of zinc(II) glycolates are the predominant reactions of these systems.

In order to find the reason for low current efficiency of acetaldehyde-zinc system, current efficiencies of this system were determined at different intervals of time and are listed in Table 2. Perusal of Table 2 reveals that the current efficiency is quite high initially but it decreases with time. The decrease in current efficiency of this system with the passage of time may be due to the reason that the product of this system gets deposited on the electrode surface and thus inhibits further dissolution of zinc,

Table 2. Current efficiencies of electrochemical reactions of acetaldehyde at zinc anode at different intervals of time

System	Time (h)	Current efficiency (gram equivalent/faraday)
Acetaldehyde	0.5	0.81
	1.0	0.54
	2.0	0.37

which leads to the decrease in the current efficiency with time. Survey of literature reveals¹⁹⁻²² that many organic compounds act as corrosion inhibitors by forming a protective layer on the metal surface. Banait *et al.*⁶ also reported the similar behaviour of hexan-1-ol, heptan-1-ol and octan-1-ol at sacrificial zinc anode.

Coordination compounds of zinc(II) glycolates :

The solid products of aldehyde/ketone-ligand-zinc systems obtained from anode compartment are insoluble in commonly used organic solvents and do not melt up to 185 °C. All the products show slight change in colour at around 185 °C.

The analytical data listed in Table 3 correspond to 1 : 2 : 1 stoichiometry of zinc, aldehyde/ketone and ligand respectively.

Infrared spectral data of the products of all these systems (except that of salicylaldehyde) show no absorption band due to carbonyl group, however, the characteristic absorption bands¹⁰⁻¹⁵ of these products appear in the regions of 1630-1420, 1105-1015 and 465-450 cm⁻¹. The bands at 1105-1015 and 465-450 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ν(C-O)Zn and ν(Zn-O) groups respectively^{6-8,10}. Comparison of these bands with those of parent glycolates show that these bands in coordination compounds have shifted to higher regions as compared to the parent glycolates.

The additional bands appearing in the region of 1630-1420 cm⁻¹ in all these products may be due to ν(C=N) and ν(C=C) stretching modes of ligand molecules⁹. These bands however, appear in slightly lower region as compared to those in the pure ligand. Appearance of the bands due to the ligand molecules and the shift of ν(C-O)Zn and ν(Zn-O) bands to higher region as compared to those in the parent zinc(II) glycolates confirm the coordination of the ligand to these glycolates.

Table 3. Electrolysis characteristics, analytical and other related data of electrolytic products of aldehyde/ketone + ligand systems at zinc anode

System	Potential applied (V)	Electricity passed (Coulombs)	Product	Colour	Elemental analysis (%) :			Current efficiency (gram equivalent faraday ⁻¹)
					Found (Calcd.)			
					Zn	C	H	
Acetaldehyde + 1,10-phenanthroline	25	680	C ₄ H ₈ O ₂ ZnC ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	Brown	18.2 (19.6)	55.4 (57.6)	3.0 (4.8)	0.64
Propionaldehyde + 1,10-phenanthroline	30	720	C ₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ ZnC ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	Brown	20.4 (18.1)	50.9 (53.1)	3.9 (4.4)	0.89
Benzaldehyde + 1,10-phenanthroline	30	680	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ ZnC ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	Brown	15.0 (14.3)	65.1 (68.2)	3.4 (4.4)	0.83
Salicylaldehyde + 1,10-phenanthroline	25	600	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₄ ZnC ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	Greenish brown	12.9 (13.4)	50.7 (53.1)	3.3 (4.1)	0.97
Cinnamaldehyde + 1,10-phenanthroline	30	680	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ ZnC ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	Light brown	13.6 (12.8)	67.3 (70.7)	3.8 (4.7)	0.78
Acetone + 1,10-phenanthroline	30	680	C ₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ ZnC ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	Brown	17.9 (18.1)	56.7 (59.8)	4.3 (5.5)	0.85
Ethyl methyl ketone + 1,10-phenanthroline	30	720	C ₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ ZnC ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	Brown	15.4 (16.8)	59.2 (61.6)	5.2 (6.1)	0.97
Isobutyl methyl ketone + 1,10-phenanthroline	30	720	C ₁₂ H ₂₄ O ₂ ZnC ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	Light brown	14.5 (14.7)	61.6 (64.6)	5.7 (7.2)	0.97
Acetaldehyde + 2,2'-bipyridyl	30	680	C ₄ H ₈ O ₂ ZnC ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	Light brown	26.0 (26.8)	65.1 (68.9)	5.1 (6.6)	0.70
Propionaldehyde + 2,2'-bipyridyl	30	720	C ₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ ZnC ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	White	19.0 (19.4)	54.2 (56.9)	4.3 (5.9)	0.98
Benzaldehyde + 2,2'-bipyridyl	30	720	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ ZnC ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	Light brown	14.9 (15.1)	62.7 (66.5)	3.1 (4.6)	0.85
Salicylaldehyde + 2,2'-bipyridyl	25	720	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₄ ZnC ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	Brownish black	13.0 (14.5)	49.1 (51.6)	3.9 (4.3)	0.98
Cinnamaldehyde + 2,2'-bipyridyl	30	680	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ ZnC ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	Light brown	12.7 (13.5)	64.9 (69.8)	4.1 (5.0)	0.77
Acetone + 2,2'-bipyridyl	25	720	C ₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ ZnC ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	Light brown	19.3 (19.4)	55.2 (59.1)	4.1 (5.0)	0.89
Ethyl methyl ketone + 2,2'-bipyridyl	30	680	C ₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ ZnC ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	Light brown	17.1 (17.9)	54.8 (59.1)	4.9 (6.6)	0.96
Isobutyl methyl ketone + 2,2'-bipyridyl	30	680	C ₁₂ H ₂₄ O ₂ ZnC ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	Light brown	14.2 (15.5)	62.1 (68.4)	6.7 (7.6)	0.98

Absence of $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ absorption band and presence of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ band and doublet due to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ stretching vibrations¹⁸ in the products of salicylaldehyde + ligand systems indicate that phenolic group is reduced at inert cathode and aldehyde group remained unaffected. The products also show absorption bands¹⁰⁻¹⁵ around 1030 and 460 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})\text{Zn}$ and $\nu(\text{Zn}-\text{O})$ stretching modes respectively. Appearance of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ bands due to the ligand molecules and presence of $\nu(\text{C}-$

$\text{O})\text{Zn}$ and $\nu(\text{Zn}-\text{O})$ bands at shifted positions reveal that the present products are the coordination compounds of zinc(II) glycolates.

Current efficiencies of all these systems are also very high (listed in Table 3). Thus the reactions leading to the formation of coordination compounds of zinc(II) glycolates are the predominant reactions of these systems.

The present studies provide a direct, single step and one pot route for the synthesis of not only zinc(II) glycolates

but their coordination compounds also which otherwise are very difficult to synthesize due to the polymer nature of metal alkoxides/glycolates.

Experimental

Reagents and solvent : Acetonitrile was dried over phosphorus pentoxide and then fractionally distilled and was used as solvent in all these reactions. Tetrabutylammonium chloride was crystallized from conductivity water, dried under vacuum at 100 °C and was used as supporting electrolyte. Other organic compounds were used as procured.

Procedure and technique :

Zinc(II) glycolates :

Electrolysis of the solutions of aldehyde/ketone (2 mL) and tetrabutylammonium chloride (500 mg) in acetonitrile (250 mL) was carried out at zinc anode and platinum cathode in a H-type pyrex glass cell. The solution was stirred thoroughly during the progress of electrolysis with the help of a magnetic stirrer. The electrolysis cell can be represented as :

where, $\text{Zn}_{(+)}$ and $\text{Pt}_{(-)}$ represent zinc anode and platinum cathode respectively. R is alkyl/aryl group and R' is alkyl/aryl group or hydrogen.

The solid products started separating in the anode compartment during the progress of electrolysis. After ten hours of electrolysis, the solid products from anode compartment were filtered, washed with hot acetonitrile and dry ether and then dried under vacuum.

Coordination compounds of zinc(II) glycolates :

The above zinc(II) glycolates were refluxed with ligands for several hours in different organic solvents. Elemental analysis and infrared spectral studies of the products reveals that the ligand molecules could not rupture the glycoxy bridging to enter coordination sphere of the glycolates. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to prepare the coordination compounds of zinc(II) glycolates *in situ* electrochemically so that the ligand molecule attach with the zinc ions before the formation of the glycoxy bridges. The solution of aldehyde/ketone, supporting elec-

trolyte and the ligand was, therefore, electrolysed at sacrificial zinc anode essentially by the same method as discussed above.

Zinc contents in the product were determined volumetrically by oxine method²³. Microanalyses for carbon and hydrogen in these products have also been conducted.

Infrared spectra of these products have been scanned in potassium bromide pellets by using Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, RXI, in the region of 4000–450 cm^{-1} .

Current efficiencies (gram equivalent of metal dissolved per faraday of electricity) of all these products were determined by electrolysing the above solutions in the similar manner at a constant current of 20 mA for two hours. The ratio of experimental and theoretical zinc contents gives the current efficiency.

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